

A Circularity Framework for emerging PBtX pathways

Methodology and application to the production of hybrid bio/e-Methanol.

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Abstract: This paper presents a novel, structured framework for the circularity assessment of emerging Power-and-Biomass-to-X (PBtX) processes, and demonstrates its application within the Horizon Europe BeBOP project (<https://www.bebop-project.eu/>), which develops a novel hybrid bio/e-Methanol production pathway at technology readiness level (TRL) 6. Existing circularity frameworks (e. g., ISO 59020, Circular Transition Indicators, Material Circularity Indicator) are designed for established companies and products, and are hardly applicable to novel industrial processes with limited operational data. The proposed seven-phase framework combines a structured application of Circular Economy principles (narrow, slow, close, regenerate) with expert workshops, development of quantitative indicators, analysis of circular business models, and the assessment of trade-offs. The application of the framework to the case of the BeBOP concept resulted in 25 circularity indicators across four life cycle stages. Feedstock quality, the maximizing of the reversible Solid Oxide Cell (rSOC) service life, heat integration and the location of the plant were identified as the most relevant and impactful circularity levers for scaling-up. The interdependency analysis revealed critical trade-offs, particularly between feedstock flexibility and process stability. This Circularity framework is transferable to other emerging PBtX technologies at low-to-medium TRLs.

Keywords: Circular Economy, Power-and-Biomass-to-X, Circularity Assessment, Methanol, Solid Oxide Cells

1 Introduction

The chemical industry is characterised as one of the hard-to-abate sectors regarding the use of fossil feedstocks and the resulting Greenhouse gas emissions (GHG). Transitioning from fossil to PBtX pathways based on renewable biomass and electricity is not merely a matter of substituting inputs but introduces fundamental process complexity:

First, basic stoichiometry imposes constraints. Producing chemicals or fuels only from biomass-derived syngas usually yields a deficit of Hydrogen relative to the required synthesis ratio. In case of Methanol, natural gas provides an optimal Hydrogen to Carbon (H/C) ratio of 4:1 compared to an H/C ratio for biomass of around 1.5:1 (Vassilev et al., 2010). Hydrogen upgrading through electrolysis is therefore necessary to achieve competitive Carbon efficiencies - a step that adds both capital cost and operational complexity

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(Rajaei et al., 2024).

Second, biomass feedstocks are inherently less homogeneous than their fossil counterparts. They carry variable ash compositions and impurities such as Chlorine, Sulphur and alkali metals, all of which have an impact on downstream process performance, gas cleaning requirements and equipment lifetime.

Third, the increased economic pressure on PBtX-pathways demand that the potentials of co-products are realised wherever possible. This relates both to typical process outputs such as excess heat or gasification ashes for soil amendment purposes, as well as to inputs such as residual biomass streams. To realise these Industrial Symbiosis potentials, the plant location becomes critically important from the outset.

Fourth, key enabling electrolysis technologies - particularly Solid Oxide Cells (SOCs) operating under real syngas conditions - introduce significant unknowns at industrial scale. Their service lifetime, degradation behaviour and interaction with upstream process variability are not yet fully understood, and the relevant expertise is typically fragmented across specialized domains (Schmidt et al., 2026).

Fifth, renewable electricity supply is inherently intermittent. A process designed around electrolysis, must accommodate fluctuating energy availability, often requiring either buffer storage, flexible load operation, or the ability to switch between operating modes - each option carrying distinct implications for process design, component lifetime and economic viability.

These complexities, combined with the inherent motivation of decarbonization, require systemic thinking and an early integration of Circular Economy (CE) principles into process design. After a concise review of existing circularity frameworks the gaps for applying them to low TRL, emerging PBtX pathways are discussed and addressed by a purpose-built seven-stage framework. The framework is applied to a hybrid bio/e-Methanol production system and the main findings are summarized. The paper is completed by discussing the applicability to other PBtX pathways and the potential value to be gained from this analysis.

2 Review of existing circularity frameworks

The CE concept proposes a systematic approach for optimizing resource flows throughout a technology's life cycle. Four core CE principles can be distinguished: narrowing (using fewer resources per unit of output), slowing (using component and products as long as possible), closing (using resources again), and regenerating (using renewable and regenerative resources) (Bocken et al., 2016).

Several frameworks exist for measuring circularity performance, among others: ISO 59020:2024 provides guidance on measuring circularity at the organizational level,

with core indicators for resource inflows, outflows, energy, water and economic dimensions (ISO, 2024). The Circular Transition Indicators (CTI) by the World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD) offer a standardized quantitative self-assessment (WBCSD, 2023). The European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS E5) mandate reporting on resource use and CE for large companies (ESRS, 2023).

However, for emerging industrial processes at low TRLs, significant application gaps persist. Most frameworks are designed for established companies assessing existing products or operations, assuming defined product boundaries, measurable flows and operational history. Indicators such as recycled content of input flows or actual lifetime vs. industry average presuppose that data from established operations exist, which is not the case at low TRLs. Furthermore, circularity frameworks providing specific guidance for the chemistry sector or industrial process equipment have not been identified. The process industries characteristics (such as continuous flow operations, high-temperature processes, industrial symbiosis potentials, consumable management) differ fundamentally from the product manufacturing contexts for which most circularity frameworks were developed.

Nevertheless, even if these circularity frameworks cannot be directly adopted, they highlight some variables that are important to consider for the process development and the plant design. The following section discusses a tailored framework developed for low TRL (PBtX) processes.

3 A novel structured framework for the circularity assessment of emerging PBtX pathways

The proposed circularity framework addresses a specific gap: how to systematically assess and improve the circularity of complex, multi-stage industrial processes at low-to-medium TRL, where operational data is scarce, expertise is fragmented across domains, and design decisions with long-term implications are being made in the present. It builds on two foundations: aligning the four CE principles as structuring elements and obtaining insights from experts as a substitute for the quantitative, process and design data that would be required.

Fig. 1: Circularity Assessment Framework for emerging PBtX processes (Own graph).

This novel circularity framework consists of seven sequential phases, each building on the outputs of the previous one, as shown in Fig. 1.

Phase 1: Applying CE strategies to the process stages: The four CE principles are mapped onto the specific process stages under investigation. For each combination of principle and process stage, areas of interest are identified.

Phase 2: Identifying and mobilizing stakeholders: For each process stage, relevant internal and external experts and stakeholders are identified and engaged for phase 3.

Phase 3: Gaining qualitative insights through targeted workshops: The workshops are organized along the life cycle stages/process stages. Each workshop should ideally cover an introduction to CE concepts and deep-dive on the technical aspects of the processes and units in that life cycle stage, to translate the CE principles into the most consequential circularity levers (providing the greatest resource efficiency benefit) of the process. Dependent on context and applicability, different tools should be encouraged in the workshops, ranging from a collection of best-practice examples and check-lists for circularity in other industries to group discussion with guided moderation.

Phase 4: Translating qualitative insights into quantitative indicators: The qualitative insights are distilled into measurable, quantitative performance indicators. Each proposed indicator is evaluated for its relevance to scale-up decisions, and its measurability with data available or from planned process implementation.

Phase 5: Evaluating circular business models (CBMs): The gained circularity insights from phase 3 are examined again, now through the lens of possible business models, to identify the stakeholders and value capture mechanisms that would incentivize a positive impact on the quantitative indicators from phase 4.

Phase 6: Analyzing trade-offs and synergies: The circularity indicators are systematically assessed to identify interdependencies, through pairwise analysis of their synergies and trade-offs.

Phase 7: Deriving recommendations for a scale-up: The combined outputs of the previous 6 phases are synthesised into actionable design recommendations, highlighting the most impactful circularity levers, the process parameters and their trade-offs that will need to be managed, and the best conditions to realize the CBMs circularity potentials.

4 Applying the circularity framework to a hybrid bio/e-Methanol process

The BeBOP project is developing a Power-and-Biomass-to-Methanol process that integrates a rSOC within the syngas conditioning line of a biomass gasifier, as well as a 3D printed Methanol reactor unit. Unlike conventional approaches that add Hydrogen from a

separate electrolysis unit, the BeBOP concept uses the rSOC to directly upgrade the syngas through co-electrolysis (SOEC), simultaneously shifting the H/C ratio, reforming residual Methane and electrochemically removing excess Oxygen. Preliminary models estimate that the biogenic Carbon retained in the final Methanol product can effectively be doubled, achieving over 90 % Carbon efficiency compared to approximately 40-45 % for conventional biomass-to-Methanol routes (Rajaei et al., 2024).

The rSOC can also operate in reverse mode as a Solid Oxide Fuel Cell (SOFC), generating electricity from syngas during periods of high demand. This is also enabled by the reactor design downstream, which allows variable loads and thus avoids the shutdown of the Methanol synthesis unit. The process is demonstrated in a 20 kW, TRL 6 pilot plant, with scale-up pathways targeting a 100 MW commercial plant. Fig. 2 gives an overview of selected process flows for the commercial scale-up (Rajaei et al., 2024).

Fig. 2: Input-output diagram of the BeBOP process scaled-up to 100 MW (Adapted from Rajaei et al., 2024)

4.1 Key findings from applying the seven phases of the Circularity framework

The application of the circularity framework to the hybrid Methanol production process was conducted between January 2025 and December 2025, engaging project consortium partners and a Stakeholder Network of 13 specialists along seven workshops. The following section describes selected insights gained in phase 3 and phase 4 of the framework along the four CE principles (Schmidt et al., 2026).

Narrowing (using less): Feedstock quality upstream emerged as the dominant efficiency lever. Clean woody biomass delivers the highest cold gas efficiency and lowest gas cleaning load, whereas secondary biomass sources introduce impurities (e. g. Chlorine and alkali metals) that would increase auxiliary energy demand and potentially reduce plant up-time. Heat reutilization from the biomass gasification was identified as the most significant onsite lever, creating direct synergies with the operation of the SOEC as a primary consumer of heat. The 3D printed Methanol reactor provides advantages to conventional reactor designs especially related to its heat transfer. Furthermore, it can operate

dynamically across 25-100 % capacity. This allows for a flexible SOFC mode, where syngas is mostly converted to electricity (e. g. in periods of high electricity prices), while a smaller sidestream of syngas is still converted to Methanol, keeping the reactor running.

Slowing (using longer): Component lifetime emerged as a primary determinant of economic viability. This is particularly relevant for the rSOC due to its high capital costs. Additionally the stack lifetime and replacement costs result in a significant component of the operational costs. SOC cells are arranged in stacks, and these are grouped into modules. The stacks are the smallest replaceable unit, requiring a dedicated maintenance strategy, also due to the heterogeneous degradation from their placing within a given module and that module's location in the syngas conditioning line. Syngas purity is the single most controllable factor influencing the rSOC's service life time, placing both a high burden on the (gas) cleaning system and the feedstock selection. For the Methanol synthesis unit, the management of the catalyst is crucial: each load exchange requires oxidation passivation of the catalyst, which can result in up to two weeks of downtime.

Closing (using again): Heat reuse offers the most beneficial potential. The exothermic reactions in the biomass gasifier and the Methanol synthesis unit are expected to generate approximately 20 MW of surplus heat, e. g., suitable for external use as district heating (Rajaei et al., 2024). To realize that potential, the plant location was identified as a key determinant. The Oxygen-enriched stream from the SOEC operation could be recycled back to the gasifier, though achieving the required Oxygen purity (95 %) is technically complex. Material recycling of decommissioned rSOC stacks would be valuable, due to the critical raw materials (CRMs) used (e. g. Yttrium, Zirconium), and generally technically feasible. Economic viability however requires large scale deployment of recycling infrastructure.

Regenerating (using renewable and regenerative sources): The BeBOP process is in principle regenerative by design, as it uses biomass and renewable electricity as inputs. This dimension could be further improved by using secondary biomass sources such as forest residues or post-used wood or other feedstocks from marginal lands (e. g., Miscanthus grown for phytoremediation purposes). Such measures would lower biomass usage competition in a world of growing pressure on biomass resources. Related to electricity the rSOC's load-following capability supports the integration with intermittent renewables. This is also supported by the design of the Methanol synthesis unit, which allows for variable loads, enabling the continuous operation (also in SOFC mode).

4.2 Key circularity indicators proposed for the hybrid bio/e-Methanol process

The application of the tailored circularity framework resulted in 25 circularity indicators across the four life cycle stages and four CE principles. Tab. 1 presents a selection of the 11 most relevant indicators proposed for the hybrid bio/e-Methanol process, evaluated for its relevance to scale-up decisions, and measurability.

Tab. 1: Selection of circularity indicators with high importance and measurability.

CE Principle	Process stage	Proposed circularity indicator	Variables and unit
Narrowing	Gasification	Cold Gas Efficiency	Chemical energy of syngas vs. feedstock (%)
	rSOC	Specific Energy Consumption	kWh/kg of H ₂ produced
	MeOH Synthesis	Conversion Efficiency to bio/e-Methanol	% of Carbon in conditioned syngas converted to bio/e-Methanol
Slowing	Feedstock	Feedstock Ash Content	% of ash content by dry weight
	Feedstock	Feedstock Impurity	Alkali Index (K, Na) and Chlorine content (wt%)
	Gasification	Gasifier Uptime	% of scheduled operational time at specification
	rSOC	rSOC Stack Degradation Rate	Ave. % loss in H ₂ production rate per 1,000 hours
Closing	rSOC	rSOC Stack Replacement Frequency	Number of stack replacements per 1,000 hours
	Gasification	Heat Reuse Efficiency	% of heat recovered and utilized onsite or externally
	rSOC	CRM Recyclability Rate	% of CRMs in rSOC stacks recoverable with existing techn.
Regenerating	rSOC	Renewable Electricity Ratio	% of total rSOC electricity from renewable sources

Beyond the identification of the 25 circularity indicators, these were analysed referencing each indicator to all the others to determine if the improvement of one indicator would influenced others positively or negatively. This systematic interdependency analysis revealed that the circularity optimization for the BeBOP process is a multi-objective problem. The most critical trade-off is observed between the feedstock flexibility and the process performance: increasing the share of secondary biomass improves regenerating indicators, but introduces higher ash and impurity content, negatively impacting cold gas efficiency, gasifier uptime, and rSOC stack degradation. A second trade-off exists between maximizing renewable electricity use and the general system stability, as intermittent electricity supply may cause thermal cycling that shortens rSOC lifetime. Conversely, heat integration is synergistic, as improvements in heat reuse help reaching multiple circularity objectives simultaneously across all life cycle stages, with few negative trade-offs.

4.3 Insights from evaluating Circular Business Models

The insights from the previous phases were evaluated in the context of two possible but

contrasting business model scenarios for a first small-scale (~ 5 MW biomass input) deployment around 2030. The scenarios for a first technology application were defined as the “Plug and Play Methanol”-scenario, exploring a modular upgrade of an existing gasification plant, while the second, “The Eternal rSOC”-scenario focused on an upgrade of a planned BtX-plant with rSOC integration to increase the carbon efficiency of the process. Outcomes from both scenarios converged on service-oriented business models, where the technology provider retains operational responsibility and the customer pays for output rather than for the ownership of the physical asset. This alignment of operational and capital expenditure incentives was identified as a precondition for realizing circularity, particularly regarding the maximisation of rSOC service life and the take-back of materials at their end of life.

5 Discussion

The application of this novel circularity framework offers several transferable insights for circularity assessments of other emerging PBtX or process-industry technologies.

As CE principles are typically applied to end-user products, their framing needs to be adjusted: “Narrowing” typically describes strategies which use less material per product, in process contexts it encompasses all improvements regarding process efficiencies and its associated demands such as heat or electricity use. “Slowing” shifts from product reuse to equipment service life, maintenance optimization and consumable management. “Closing” emphasises industrial symbiosis and heat integration rather than product take-back. “Regenerating” extends beyond renewable energy to feedstock sourcing strategies and cascading use.

At early TRLs, structured expert engagement (e. g., through targeted and moderated workshops) helps obtaining process insights and information to partly compensate the lack of real, measured data. The three-part workshop format used, covering an introduction on CE, a technology deep-dive, and a moderated discussion of the CE principles, proved very engaging and effective for extracting actionable knowledge from domain experts, who also become more familiar with circularity principles and indicators.

The interdependency analysis as a planning tool helps identifying trade-offs and synergies between circularity indicators, to prevent process sub-optimization. For the case of the hybrid bio/e-Methanol BeBOP process, this holistic analysis revealed that feedstock quality is a system-wide lever affecting other indicators across all life cycle stages; a finding that would not have emerged from assessing process stages in isolation.

At low TRLs the circularity indicators were developed based on the circularity framework and the input from experts. As the PBtX technologies mature, indicators would transition to semi-quantitative estimates, and then fully measured indicator values. The original set of indicators may evolve as operational experience reveals new circularity levers.

6 Conclusions

Existing circularity frameworks investigated are not fully applicable to emerging PBtX and industrial processes at low TRLs. They demand data, operational history and system boundaries unavailable for novel processes. This contribution presented a seven-phase circularity framework that bridges this gap, by combining a structured application of CE principles with expert-driven validation, development of quantitative indicator, business model analysis, and the assessment trade-off and synergies.

The circularity framework was applied to the BeBOP hybrid bio/e-Methanol production process. Highly relevant circularity levers are the feedstock quality, the longevity of the SOC, the heat integration, and the plant location. The results also include 25 circularity indicators across the four CE principles, ranked into a selection of 11 practicable indicators, according to their relevance and the feasibility for data acquisition to evaluate them.

The application of the framework revealed as well that circularity optimization in complex PBtX processes is inherently a multi-objective problem, where trade-offs, particularly between feedstock sources and process stability, would need to be properly managed.

The results from applying this circularity framework will also feed into the project's Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Techno-Economic Analysis and business cases for exploitation.

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